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पेटेंट कार्यालय का एक प्रकाशन
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(54) Title of the invention : POLYMER COMPOSITES, MULTIWALL CARBON NANOTUBE/GRAPHENE NANOCOMPOSITES CONSISTING OF POLYMER

<p>(51) International classification :C08J0005060000, C08J0005000000, D04H0013000000, C08K0003040000, C04B0035800000</p> <p>(86) International Application No :NA Filing Date :NA</p> <p>(87) International Publication No : NA</p> <p>(61) Patent of Addition to Application Number :NA Filing Date :NA</p> <p>(62) Divisional to Application Number :NA Filing Date :NA</p>	<p>(71)Name of Applicant : 1)ARUN KUMAR SHARMA Address of Applicant :B-1219,B-block sagartaal road,near sagartaal chauraha Anand nagar,bahodapur gwalior -----</p> <p>Name of Applicant : NA Address of Applicant : NA</p> <p>(72)Name of Inventor : 1)Arun Kumar Sharma Address of Applicant :B 1219,B block, anand nagar ,Bahodapur gwalior Gwalior -----</p> <p>2)Dr. Rakesh Bhandari Address of Applicant :187,Vakil colony,Bhilwara,311001 Bhilwara -----</p> <p>3)Shri krishna Dhakad Address of Applicant :B-6, Block-A,UIT RGPV Shivpuri Campus,Shivpuri Shivpuri -----</p> <p>4)Sarika sharma Address of Applicant :B 1219,B block, anand nagar ,Bahodapur gwalior Gwalior -----</p> <p>5)Dr. Camelia Pinca – Bretotean Address of Applicant :Ap.16, Bl.3 ,nr.7,Str. Republicii, Hunedoara, 331032 -----</p>
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(57) Abstract :
Natural fibres in composites are seen as a good choice over synthetic fibre for making composites. They have inferior mechanical as well as interfacial attributes because the contact between the fibres and the matrix is weak and the orientation of the fibres varies. Natural jute fibre composites made with graphene and Multiwall carbon nanotube (MWCNT) that have improved mechanical properties and performance are focus of this invention. The fibres are arranged into a jute mat in a systematic direction, in epoxy matrix. Because of this, these composites with better performance could be used in a variety of ways. In this invention Disclosed a Jute, Graphene and MWCNT reinforced epoxy based composite material that exhibits high flexural properties. Jute, Graphene and MWCNT are incorporated in the thermosetting polymeric matrix phase to make hybrid composites. It is an object of this invention to provide hybrid composites of having excellent flexural characteristics, made by using a hand lay-up method.

Figure : 1

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